

To:
Huiqing Wang

cc:
Maarten Hornikx

Ethical Review Board

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Date	Reference
August 29, 2024	ERB2024BE52

Ethical review research proposal

Dear Huiqing,

It is a pleasure to inform you that the Ethical Review Board (ERB) has discussed and approves your application.

Furthermore, the Board wants to draw your attention to the terms and conditions in the appendix.

Success with your research!

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'D. Lakens'.

Dr. D. Lakens
Chair Ethical Review Board TU/e

Enclosures
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The ERB retains the right to revise its decision regarding the implementation and the WMO¹/WMH² status of any research study in response to changing regulations, research activities, or other unforeseen circumstances that are relevant to reviewing any such study. The ERB shall notify the principal researcher of its revised decision and of the reasons for having revised its decision.

¹WMO: Law on Medical Scientific Research involving Human Beings (in Dutch: Wet medisch-wetenschappelijk onderzoek met mensen)

²WMH: Medical Device Directive (in Dutch: Wet op de medische hulpmiddelen)

APPENDIX 1

Terms and conditions

Amendments

When considerable amendments are made to the design of the study or educational activity, or when the time period between ERB approval and start of the study is longer than one year, please consult the ERB.

Privacy and research data management

The ERB would like to point out that collecting, handling and storing personal information is subject to the General Data Protection Regulation. Please visit TU/e intranet for the latest information and regulations on www.tue.nl/rdm